

MOTIVATE XR

Maintenance, Support & Operation Training using Immersive Virtual and Augmented Technology for Efficiency with XR

D2.1 - COMMUNICATION KIT V1

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Abstract	The deliverable D2.1 introduces the MOTIVATE XR Communication Plan which is a comprehensive and living document that outlines the tools, channels, and activities to be put in place throughout the project to ensure successful and consistent visual representation of the MOTIVATE XR, as well as its activities for successful dissemination of results.
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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present document D2.1 introduces the MOTIVATE XR Communication Kit (V1), which is a comprehensive and living document that outlines the tools, channels, and activities established throughout the project to ensure successful and consistent representation of the MOTIVATE XR project, as well as its activities. It defines the communication strategy as well as the timing of the various activities throughout the project lifetime.

By leveraging diverse channels and tailored messaging, the communication plan aims to maximise the impact and reach of MOTIVATE XR's innovations. The set of rules and procedures described and presented within this document will guide MOTIVATE XR's partners through effective communication with target audiences. Regular reviews and updates will ensure the plan and strategies remain adaptive to new opportunities and evolving project dynamics.

This deliverable consists of the following sections:

- **Chapter 1 - Introduction:** provides an overview of the project and outlines the communication objectives developed to align with the project aims.
- **Chapter 2 - Communication Kit:** highlights MOTIVATE XR brand identity, communication material and digital presence including its website, social media channels and other additional platforms.
- **Chapter 3 - Methodology and Approach:** outlines the content strategy and planning adopted to successfully achieve MOTIVATE XR communication activities, elaborate on the timeline and the target audience with whom we will engage.
- **Chapter 4 - Monitoring and Evaluation:** outlines the communication action plan, reporting guidelines as well as the main communication key performance indicators that will be monitored throughout the project.
- **Chapter 5 - Conclusion:** summarises the content within this document.

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ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Title
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CA	Consortium Agreement
CG	Communication Goals
CO	Communication Objectives
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
SMEs	Small and Medium Enterprises
SO	Specific Objectives
VR	Virtual Reality
WP	Work Package
XR	Extended Reality

1 INTRODUCTION

Extended Reality (XR) has the potential to revolutionise various industrial sectors by completely changing the way we learn, train, and work. As VR and XR technology continues to gain traction in various industries such as manufacturing, education, and commerce, companies are recognising the immense potential of reducing costs, improving operations and customer experience. However, XR's complexity, time-consuming creation, and high costs, limit its adoption in industries that lack the expertise and resources to develop and deploy these XR experiences.

With the growing need for user-friendly XR tools across European Industries for training and on-site support, Europe must take proactive steps to develop its own XR solutions. MOTIVATE XR strategic challenge is precisely to contribute to the necessary effort to address this demand issue with an intuitive and cost-effective European XR solution tailored for industrial operations. The aim is to develop a leading XR tool suite for training and assisting in industrial operations like assembly, manufacturing, maintenance, and dismantling. This innovative, open, and highly interoperable solution is designed for users without programming skills, from large European industries to individual handypersons.

1.1 COMMUNICATION IMPORTANCE AND EU OBLIGATIONS

Effective communication is essential for the success of any project, encompassing both internal dialogue within the project consortium and external engagement with relevant stakeholders and target groups. Rigorous and precise internal communication enables the consortium to promptly address and mitigate risks, ensuring that all parties understand their roles within the project and how to effectively communicate about it. On the other hand, effective external communication not only fulfils the contractual obligations associated with the EU funding - such as seeking approval from fund operators for project timeframe extensions - but also plays a critical role in ensuring that the project outcomes reach the intended audiences.

Project beneficiaries of EU funding must promote their grants and comply with specific visibility requirements (section 2.1.6). Project partners should familiarise themselves with the necessary logos and wording to avoid serious consequences, such as grant recalculation or fund recovery. These requirements apply not only to external communications but also to internal documentation, including reports and summaries. Items subject to visibility standards include event registration sheets, invitations, promotional materials, online content, and presentations related to the project. Adhering to these guidelines is crucial for compliance and the effective communication and dissemination of project outcomes.

1.2 COMMUNICATION OBJECTIVES

Defining communication objectives is essential to provide clear goals that guide messaging and strategies and ensure that key information is effectively conveyed to the target audiences. These goals will also facilitate measurement and evaluation of the communication efforts' impact and success.

As stated in the Grant Agreement (GA), WP2 - T2.1 - Communication, Dissemination and Outreach, aims to create and execute a dissemination and communication strategy to boost the project's visibility and impact, especially among the general public, key industry, and scientific stakeholders. Essential activities include developing a visual identity, enhancing MOTIVATE XR online presence via social media, website, and promoting project achievements through publications and conference presentations, organisation of demonstrator events, technological workshops for SMEs etc. A biannual newsletter is also planned to report on key activities, progress and related events throughout the project's duration.

Specific Objectives (SO) are mentioned in the GA for communication purposes:

- **SO1:** Promoting awareness through effective communication methods and the dissemination of scientific information.
- **SO2:** Involving key stakeholders and European organisations in an Open Community to present the project to a broader audience and leverage their expertise.

To maximise our communication effort and reach, specific Communication Goals (CG) aligned with the above SOs have been defined based on influence behaviour, shape opinions, and raise awareness among targeted groups:

- **CG1:** Establish internal communication strategies among consortium partners to ensure seamless collaboration and information sharing.
- **CG2:** Facilitate the external promotion of MOTIVATE XR and its deliverables, managing branding and enhancing visibility in the XR technology sector.
- **CG3:** Educate non-specialised audience about the value added by MOTIVATE XR tools.
- **CG4:** Reach out to mid-sized companies, SMEs, and start-ups engaged in XR technologies, to cultivate an EU network of innovators and developers while promoting the adoption of the XR technology system.
- **CG5:** Raise awareness and interest in the MOTIVATE XR objectives, progress and achievements among industry professionals, policymakers and the public by conveying key messages about the project.
- **CG6:** Influence opinions and behaviours by offering valuable insights and recommendations to policymakers and industry professionals, encouraging the adoption of MOTIVATE XR solutions and best practices, ultimately demonstrating how EU funding plays a vital role in addressing societal challenges.

These goals follow a strategic framework: understanding the purpose of the communication actions (**Why**); defining the message and content to be communicated (**What**); identifying the target

audience **(to Whom)**; selecting the method of communication **(How)**; and determining the timing of the activities **(When)**.

2 COMMUNICATION KIT

2.1 BRAND IDENTITY

The development of a visual identity and a project logo ensures project outputs are consistent and easily recognisable. It is a language that communicates the project's philosophy and values, establishes the project's voice, and builds an emotional and professional connection with the target audiences. All the communication materials developed were made available to the partners through the project's [SharePoint WP2- Communication Kit](#) folder.

2.1.1 LOGO

The logo is a key component of the project's visual identity. It facilitates memory and recognition and must be featured in all external communications and dissemination activities related to the project.

The official logo of the project (Fig.1) displays the project's graphic visual, and acronym along with its definition. To facilitate the application and positioning of the logo across various platforms, 3 distinct versions of the logo were developed (Fig.2).

The symbol chosen is shaped after the silhouette of XR headset glasses, to represent the core area of work, with the addition of a hand icon, to reinforce the idea of immersion, and the cogwheel for the industrial context. A varied colour palette was selected to evoke the richness of the interaction of analogue reality with digital reality. The variety of colours are also a statement for accessibility for a wide skill range of users.

FIGURE 1: MOTIVATE XR OFFICIAL LOGO

FIGURE 2: MOTIVATE XR LOGO VARIATIONS

Several versions of the logo were created (for each version) to adapt on several backgrounds:

- Secondary colour to adapt on bright or dark backgrounds (Fig.3)
- Monochromatic logos (Fig.4)
- Black and white (greyscale) logos (Fig.5)

FIGURE 3: MOTIVATE XR SECONDARY COLOUR CONFIGURATION

FIGURE 4: MOTIVATE XR MONOCHROMATIC LOGOS

FIGURE 5: MOTIVATE XR BLACK AND WHITE LOGOS

2.1.2 BRAND BOOK

To ensure and maintain consistency in the use of the visual identity, a brand book was created for partners to refer to with precise instructions whenever creating any visual material. When using the logo, partners should use their judgement to determine the most appropriate logo to use. A fundamental rule, partners should always keep in mind, is that the logo must be legible, as stated in the principle: "If you can't read it, you can't use it."

To ensure clarity, partners should use the logo at the correct size and resolution for all promotional activity. For this reason, a minimum logo size was identified (Fig.6) and examples on how the logo **should in any way be altered or rotated** (Fig.7) is provided along with other mandatory instructions.

FIGURE 6: MOTIVATE XR DEFINED LOGO MINIMUM SIZE

FIGURE 7: MOTIVATE XR LOGO ALTERATION – NOT ACCEPTABLE ACCORDING TO THE BRAND BOOK

2.1.3 COLOUR PALETTE

The choice of colour scheme is a vital aspect of our project, as it plays a significant role in conveying the intended message effectively. To achieve this, a tailored colour palette was chosen to embody a harmonious and consistent visual identity, reflecting the brand’s core values and messaging. By opting for a diverse colour palette, we aim to capture the dynamic interplay between analogue and digital realities, while also demonstrating accessibility for users with varying skills levels.

All project partners are requested to use the following colour palette for any promotional material (graphics, background colour etc.) developed for communication purposes.

FIGURE 8: MOTIVATE XR COLOUR PALETTE

2.1.4 TYPOGRAPHY

Barlow is a practical sans serif font identified as the ideal choice for MOTIVATE XR. It strikes a perfect balance between friendliness and functionality, making it an excellent option for MOTIVATE XR looking to create a logo that communicates simplicity and warmth brand personality.

Due to its wide range of weights and styles, Barlow is also perfect for complex websites, app interfaces as text, or display fonts. Here below some of the variations:

Barlow for digital and print materials

Free download at [Google Fonts](#)

Barlow Bold	AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIiJjKkLlMmNnOoPpQqRrSsTtUuVvWwXxYyZz
Barlow Regular	AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIiJjKkLlMmNnOoPpQqRrSsTtUuVvWwXxYyZz
Barlow Light	AaBbCcDdEeFfGgHhIiJjKkLlMmNnOoPpQqRrSsTtUuVvWwXxYyZz

FIGURE 9: MOTIVATE XR TYPOGRAPHY

2.1.5 VISUAL ELEMENTS

Incorporating icons into promotional materials and on the website significantly enhances visual communication by conveying complex information quickly and efficiently. Icons make content more engaging and improve user experience through easier navigation. They help create a cohesive brand identity while reducing clutter and enhancing readability. Consistent use of icons across platforms reinforces brand recognition and improves user engagement. Below in Figure 10. is an overview of some of the icons created for MOTIVATE XR.

FIGURE 10: MOTIVATE XR ICONS

2.1.6 EU FUNDING AND ACKNOWLEDGEMENT INFORMATION

A copy of the EU emblem and a caption stating that the project has received funding from the European Union must be included in all communication or dissemination material of the project. The EU emblem should be used along with the following caption (Fig.11):

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

FIGURE 11: EU EMBLEM AND FUNDING CAPTION

2.2 COMMUNICATION MATERIALS

To facilitate the efficient and unified implementation of the MOTIVATE XR project, a set of standardised templates were developed and made available to all partners. These templates serve as vital resources to maintain consistency, professionalism, and efficiency in all communication and documentation related to the project. The collection includes a Word Template (Fig.12) intended for general document creation, such as simple reports and meeting minutes; a Deliverable Template (Fig.13), specifically designed for project deliverables; and a Presentation Template (Fig.14) in PowerPoint, tailored for use in meetings, workshops, and conferences.

2.2.1 TEMPLATES

[Word Document - Simple Document and Meeting Minutes Templates](#)

FIGURE 14: MOTIVATE XR PPT PRESENTATION TEMPLATE

2.2.2 PROMOTIONAL MATERIALS: VISUALS AND GRAPHICS

Flyer and roll-up

To support the project's visual identity in a holistic way, a MOTIVATE XR flyer and roll-up were developed and can be printed if partners require any material to promote at a physical event. They are designed to attract attention and effectively communicate the project's goals and ambitions but also provide an overview of the project pilots and partners. These promotional materials are also available for download on the website, in the [Open Community](#) section.

FIGURE 15: MOTIVATE XR FLYER AND ROLL-UP

Project Presentation

Preparing a project presentation at an early stage is crucial for achieving clarity and alignment on project objectives and facilitating collaboration among partners. It serves not only as a promotional tool to attract stakeholders and boost visibility but also facilitates engagement by clearly conveying the project's value, ensuring consistency in messaging across diverse events and engagement. This presentation serves as a reference for guiding future actions, helping avoid miscommunication and scope changes. It prepares partners to effectively present the project at events, allowing for a cohesive representation and maximising impact. The project presentation comprises of various slides such as a brief introduction of the project, its objectives and ambitions, the prestige consortium partners and an overview of MOTIVATE XR 5 complementary pilots.

FIGURE 16: MOTIVATE XR PROJECT PRESENTATION

Social Media Banners

Coherent social media banner design enhances brand identity, ensuring consistent visual messaging that resonates with audiences across various platforms (YouTube, X, and LinkedIn). This consistency fosters recognition and trust, making it easier for the audience to identify and engage with the brand. Well-designed banners can capture attention quickly, increasing the likelihood of shares and interactions.

FIGURE 17: MOTIVATE XR YOUTUBE BANNER

FIGURE 18: MOTIVATE XR X BANNER

FIGURE 19: MOTIVATE XR LINKEDIN BANNER

Social Media Visuals

Various customised graphics were developed for social media platforms such as LinkedIn and X, to ensure a cohesive and engaging online presence.

FIGURE 20: MOTIVATE XR SOCIAL MEDIA VISUALS

Background Conference Call Banner

A customised visual background was developed for partners to use for online meetings, ensuring coherence and consistency with the brand identity and professionalism.

FIGURE 21: MOTIVATE XR BACKGROUND CONFERENCE CALL BANNER

2.3 DIGITAL PRESENCE

2.3.1 WEBSITE

The MOTIVATE XR website (www.motivatexr.eu) launched M4 of the project, serves as a vital cornerstone for the project's communication and outreach strategy. It is essential for facilitating communication, enhancing engagement and supporting the overall success of the project. Its multifaceted role (1) serves as a central hub for information, resources and stakeholder engagement, and (2) ensures that stakeholders are continuously and accurately informed, actively involved, and empowered to contribute to the project's objectives.

The importance of the MOTIVATE XR website includes several key aspects:

1. **Central Information Hub:** the website is the primary repository for all project-related information, consolidating essential details such as goals, progress update, deliverables, and news. It ensures that stakeholders have ready access to accurate and up-to-date information, fostering transparency and keeping everyone informed about the project's direction.
2. **Professional Image and Trust Building:** a well-designed, user-friendly website reflects the professionalism and credibility of the MOTIVATE XR project. It establishes a polished visual presence that reinforces the project's brand identity and instils trust among stakeholders. A site that is consistently updated and aesthetically appealing contributes to a positive perception of the project's integrity and competence.
3. **Stakeholder Engagement:** by providing a robust platform for interaction, the website facilitates active engagement among a diverse audience, including industry professionals, academic institutions, policymakers, and the public. Features like newsletters, blog articles and contact forms encourage ongoing communication and feedback, allowing stakeholders to share their insights and stay connected with the project.
4. **Resource Distribution and Accessibility:** the website serves as a centralised location for distributing educational and promotional materials, including reports, whitepapers, brochures, and multimedia content. This approach simplifies access for users, enabling them to easily find and download relevant resources. By enhancing resource accessibility, the website supports knowledge dissemination and encourages broader participation in the project.
5. **Global Visibility and Awareness:** the website automatically and significantly boosts the visibility of the project on a global scale. By effectively showcasing its goals, activities, and achievements, the website helps to raise awareness and attract interest from potential partners, participants, and supporters. This visibility is instrumental in building a strong community around the project and fostering collaboration.
6. **Up-to-Date with Project:** to keep stakeholders continuously informed and engaged, the website will regularly publish on project milestones, achievements, and future activities. This consistent flow of information is crucial to foster a sense of community and involvement and ensure that stakeholders feel connected to the project's progress.
7. **Event Promotion and Engagement:** the website serves as a dedicated platform to promote various events, such as webinars, workshops, and conferences. It delivers essential

information regarding registrations, agenda, and speakers, helping to maximise participation and engagement. By centralising event details, the website ensures that stakeholders can easily find opportunities to connect and contribute.

8. **Training Access - by MOTIVATE XR:** the website will offer a comprehensive pack of training tools and resources. This online platform aims to enhance the learning experience and provide access to specialised training programs.

In essence the MOTIVATE XR website is a key hub for communication, engagement and knowledge sharing. It plays a vital role in raising awareness of the project, demonstrating its activities, and keeping all stakeholders updated and connected with the ongoing project's efforts and progress. During the project execution Open Community and XR Training will be developed and offered as another functionality of the MOTIVATE XR website. Given the evolving nature of the project and associated activities, it is crucial that the website is constantly updated with relevant content and accurately capture its progress and foster lasting engagement among stakeholders.

FIGURE 22: MOTIVATE XR WEBSITE OVERVIEW

2.3.2 F6S PLATFORM

F6S (www.f6s.com) is the largest and fastest-growing social platform for founders and startups, with over 1.7 million users and more than 200,000 startups and SMEs, establishing itself as the #1 startup community globally. Through F6S, MOTIVATE XR can connect with an additional 250,000 users and 30,000 startups and SMEs across Europe with over 7,000 investors.

MOTIVATE XR project is featured on the F6S innovation website project section, among other European Union funded initiatives. This attributed space features a short introduction of the project, including a link to the website.

FIGURE 23: F6S INNOVATION WEBSITE FEATURING MOTIVATE XR

2.3.3 SOCIAL MEDIA

LinkedIn Page

LinkedIn is our primary social media platform due to its extensive networking opportunities, which allows us to connect with key individuals who are relevant to our project. By using LinkedIn, we can effectively engage with decision-makers, influencers, and industry leaders, ensuring our outreach is both strategic and impactful. This targeted approach not only enhances our visibility among potential collaborators but also fosters meaningful connections that could contribute to the success of our initiatives.

[MOTIVATE XR LinkedIn](#)

The number of followers as on September 27, 2024 (M4): 180

FIGURE 24: MOTIVATE XR LINKEDIN PAGE

X Page

In addition, X (previously known as Twitter) was chosen alongside LinkedIn to engage in real-time conversations and reach a broader audience. X allows us to share updates, participate in trending discussions, and amplify our message, thereby strengthening our online presence. This dual-platform strategy ensures effective networking and community engagement across both platforms.

MOTIVATE XR X

The number of followers as on September 27, 2024 (M4): 42

FIGURE 25: MOTIVATE XR X PAGE

YouTube Account

A YouTube account was created to share audio-visual content generated within the project. A total of 3 videos will be developed during the project lifetime and made available to the public. However, the number of videos can vary depending on the progress of the project, video content could include an overview of the project, training or pilots' educational videos. These videos will also be displayed on MOTIVATE XR website and promoted on social media platforms - LinkedIn and X.

MOTIVATE XR YouTube

FIGURE 26: MOTIVATE XR YOUTUBE ACCOUNT

2.3.4 NEWSLETTER - MAILCHIMP

The MOTIVATE XR project’s newsletter is a vital communication tool aimed at keeping stakeholders in the loop about the project’s journey, accomplishments, and relevant industry news. Scheduled for biannual releases (M6, M12, M18, M24, M30 and M36) until May 2027, each edition will align with important project phases and events, spotlighting milestones, progress updates, and the latest trends in the XR industry. Contributions from project partners will help create rich content and foster a spirit of collaboration.

Crafted to be visually appealing and engaging, the newsletter will leverage Mailchimp to ensure a smooth reading experience on any device. A subscription display was already made available while the website was under construction (Fig.27) and it is now available on the website (Fig.28) on the home page and also through a [dedicated page](#) created to work with the Linktree (section 2.3.6) - subscribers only need to provide their name and email - and all data collected will be securely stored in accordance with GDPR regulations, with an easy unsubscribe option in every issue. As on September 27, 2024, MOTIVATE XR has 24 subscribers (Fig.29).

The newsletter will reach subscribers' inboxes directly, be promoted across social media (LinkedIn), and archived on the project’s website for easy public access. By personalising content, we aim to enhance readers’ engagement, and we encourage partners to share the newsletter within their own networks. Ultimately, the MOTIVATE XR project newsletter plays a crucial role in keeping stakeholders connected, cultivating a sense of community, and sharing valuable insights from the industry.

FIGURE 27: SUBSCRIBE TO NEWSLETTER WHILE WEBSITE WAS UNDER CONSTRUCTION

FIGURE 28: SUBSCRIBE TO NEWSLETTER ON WEBSITE

FIGURE 29: SUBSCRIBERS MAILCHIMP

2.3.5 OPENAIRE - ZENODO

Following the Grant Agreement (GA), MOTIVATE XR will be aligned with the principles of Open Science, using OpenAIRE’s Zenodo as its open access repository and communication channel to demonstrate its presence within the scientific community.

Zenodo provides a solid and reliable platform for the storage and sharing of research outputs, ensuring easy access to all public deliverables of MOTIVATE XR. By using Zenodo, MOTIVATE XR ensures that its research findings and results are openly accessible to a broad audience, thereby enhancing integrity and reliability in research by implementing best practices that improve the traceability, transparency, and accessibility of scientific results.

FIGURE 30: MOTIVATE XR ZENODO ACCOUNT

2.3.6 LINKTREE

Linktree is a versatile tool that allows users to consolidate multiple links into one single URL, ultimately simplifying the sharing of content across various platforms. It offers analytics tracking to monitor link performance, is optimised for mobile devices and allows easy updates without changing the main URL.

A [Linktree](#) (Fig.31) was created for MOTIVATE XR regrouping our digital presence ([website](#), [LinkedIn](#), [X](#), [YouTube](#), [Mailchimp subscription](#) and [mailing](#)). This will be a valuable tool for increasing engagement and streamlining our online presence. To enhance accessibility, we created a QR code (Fig.32) that directs users straight to our Linktree page. This QR code will be used on various promotional materials (flyer, roll-up, ppt presentation, posters etc.), at events and shared on social media visuals, making it easy for followers to scan and quickly access our combined information in one place directly from their mobile device.

FIGURE 31: MOTIVATE XR LINKTREE PAGE

FIGURE 32: MOTIVATE XR LINKTREE QR CODE

3 METHODOLOGY AND APPROACH

The objective of MOTIVATE XR’s communication is to enhance awareness and generate interest in the project and its activities. This includes specific strategies for promoting both the project and its outcomes. Consequently, communication plays a vital role in supporting dissemination and exploitation activities (to be elaborated in D2.9). It will offer cross-project assistance for textual and graphic promotions, as well as for the development and upkeep of promotional materials.

MOTIVATE XR’s communication efforts are deeply rooted in the project’s objectives and associated KPIs. To ensure alignment with these objectives and KPIs, the purpose of the communication plan is to engage a wider audience beyond the core MOTIVATE XR community. This will be achieved through delivering well-crafted messages through effective channels to effectively reach target audiences and foster interaction with key stakeholders.

Throughout the project lifetime, various communication campaigns will be developed and executed to effectively engage the target audience (section 3.3), with particular emphasis on the different phases of the project, such as the project 5 complementary pilots and other important developments.

3.1 CONTENT STRATEGY AND PLANNING

To effectively convey the scope, objectives, achievements, and impact of the MOTIVATE XR project, a variety of content types must be created. Each content type serves a distinct role in capturing the audience’s attention, fostering engagement, and maintaining their interest. Guided by the communication methodology and target audience analysis, the content strategy adopts a human-centric approach, using a light, engaging tone for non-technical audiences and fostering clear, open conversation for technical stakeholders. Below are the content types that are currently being developed for MOTIVATE XR.

Content Goals	Content Types	Description
Awareness – Inform and Attract	Educational content about project scope and objectives	Engage and enlighten stakeholders regarding the project’s aims, initiatives, and importance. Raise awareness among the audience on XR technology expanding the ecosystem and how MOTIVATE XR contributes to tackling existing challenges.
	Partners’ expertise and contribution to the project	Elaborate on partners’ expertise and contribution. Highlight consortium diverse

		strengths and enhance credibility through testimonials from partners.
Empower - Project Credibility	Blog posts, Articles, Success Stories, and Case Studies	<p>Capture audience attention with detailed analysis, valuable insights, and real-life examples tied to the project.</p> <p>Highlight project results and key findings on social media channels, project website and newsletter.</p>
Retention - Audience Interest	Email Marketing, Media Advertising, and Retargeting Campaigns	Maintain audience interest with personalised messaging and content to increase traffic to the MOTIVATE XR website, motivate sign-ups for newsletter or webinars, and highlight project achievements or events.
Engage - Collaboration	Events, Workshops and Conferences	<p>Engage and connect with stakeholders during events. Communicate on the project objectives, outcomes and tools.</p> <p>Elaborate on opportunities for knowledge sharing, networking and collaborations.</p>

TABLE 1: MOTIVATE XR CONTENT STRATEGY

Channels	Frequency of Posts
LinkedIn and X	At least twice per week
Website Blog Article	At least once a month

TABLE 2: CHANNELS POST FREQUENCY

Considering the project’s flexibility, the frequency of posts may need to be adjusted to maintain their relevance and effectiveness. This allows us to better align our strategy with current practices and audience expectations.

3.1.1 Campaign Strategy

As part of the communication plan, MOTIVATE XR has developed 2 types of campaigns for the first stage of the project to increase awareness, drive traffic and engage with stakeholders. More campaigns are planned to be deployed during the lifetime of the project. Table 3. displays the list of campaigns that have already started and a few examples of posts (Fig.33).

Campaign	Topic	Proposed Month
Introduction	Project Launch Website Launch Meet the Partners	M1-M4
Awareness	Subscribe to Newsletter Project Objectives Project Pilots	From M3-M6

TABLE 3: MOTIVATE XR CAMPAIGN STRATEGY

FIGURE 33: SOCIAL MEDIA POST EXAMPLES

3.2 TIMELINE OF COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

The communication activities of MOTIVATE XR are strategically scheduled based on the project's development phases. While a considerable number of communication initiatives will take place during the project's initial stages to promote awareness of MOTIVATE XR, the most impactful dissemination efforts will occur as intermediate and final research and innovation results become available.

Figure 34. outlines the anticipated frequency and tentative timelines for the communication activities related to MOTIVATE XR. The frequency and content of these activities will be consistently reviewed and evaluated, enabling us to make necessary adjustments and modifications in aligning with the project’s progress and evolving needs.

FIGURE 34: TIMELINE COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

3.3 TARGET AUDIENCE

Gaining insights into the MOTIVATE XR target audience and customising our communication efforts to meet the specific needs of each segment is the initial step in creating an effective communication plan - aligning the project’s objectives, messaging, and design with the preferences, needs, and behaviours of the intended users or consumers.

Understanding the audience allows for tailored strategies that enhance engagement, improve user experience, and increase the likelihood of success. By identifying demographics, motivations, and pain points early on, project teams can make informed decisions, allocate resources effectively, and create relevant content or products that resonate, ultimately driving better outcomes and fostering stronger connections with the audience.

MOTIVATE XR has identified the below target audiences:

Content Producers and Creative Agencies: content producers will find that the authoring and publishing tools available for XR experiences significantly enhance their workflow. These features will empower individuals who may not possess programming expertise to easily conceptualise and disseminate their creative ideas. *As a result, a broader range of content producers can engage with and contribute to the expanding XR landscape.*

Developers of XR Technologies: the open architecture of MOTIVATE XR, along with its commitment to established standards and the intention to collaborate with third-party partners, fosters a sustainable business ecosystem. Such an environment will empower third-party developers focusing on XR technologies - ranging from hardware devices and digital content to software extensions - to innovate and produce new products that are fully compatible with the provided suite

of tools. This approach not only enhances creativity but also ensures a diverse and robust marketplace for XR solutions.

Industry Specialist (from a wide range of domains): experts from diverse sectors collaborate to enhance MOTIVATE XR solutions tailored specifically for industrial applications. This technology is designed to create cutting-edge training programs and support systems that not only benefit employees but also improve customer experience. By integrating interactive and immersive elements, MOTIVATE XR facilitates hands-on learning and real-time assistance in complex tasks, ultimately aiming to boost productivity and efficiency while fostering a deeper understanding of operational processes among personnel and clients alike.

General Public: the general public represents a significant client base that stands to benefit from immersive XR experiences developed by manufacturers. These experiences are designed to facilitate product assembly, enhance maintenance procedures, and empower individuals to perform self-repair operations with greater ease. By leveraging augmented and virtual reality technologies, consumers can gain a deeper understanding of complex tasks, ultimately leading to increased satisfaction and reduced reliance on professional services

Policy Makers: policy makers can leverage MOTIVATE XR technology to create immersive visualisation and simulations of various scenarios, providing a clearer understanding of complex issues. By overlaying real-time data onto actual physical environments, MOTIVATE XR facilitates enhanced monitoring of resources and operations. This advanced approach empowers decision-makers to analyse situations more effectively and make well-informed choices that can positively impact communities and projects.

Training Centres: MOTIVATE XR aims to significantly lower corporate training and travel expenses by utilising XR-based training solutions. Instead of incurring costs for staff and faculty journeys to physical training centres or operational sites, these immersive training programs can be effectively conducted at local offices or even remotely from employees' homes. This approach not only enhances accessibility but also maximises efficiency, allowing for a more streamlined training process.

Students and Long-life Learning Community: this audience group benefits significantly from MOTIVATE XR, as it not only boosts learning effectiveness and retention but also encourages growth through the valuable insights gained from mistakes. The immersive nature of this training approach often makes the learning experience more engaging and enjoyable compared to traditional methods. As a result, careers facing skill shortages become more enticing, attracting individuals who may have considered these paths otherwise.

EU XR Initiatives & Networks: MOTIVATE XR intends to collaborate with European initiatives and networks like [XR4Europe](#), which connects XR professionals and organisations, as well as [XR4HUMAN](#), which is dedicated to establishing ethical standards for XR development. By building these partnerships, MOTIVATE XR aims to create synergies with various EU projects (e.g. [XR2Learn](#), [ARTwin AR](#), [Iv4XR](#), [TACTILITY](#), [XR4ED](#), [VoxReality...](#)) that enable the exchange of knowledge and best practices, fostering innovation and ethical practices in the XR field.

Scientific Community: MOTIVATE XR is dedicated to promoting collaboration among researchers and technicians across the globe. By enabling these professionals to co-create solutions, MOTIVATE XR not only enhances research outcomes but also empowers individuals with limited technical skills. [This initiative ensures that a diverse audience can effectively utilise our tools to advance their own research initiatives, fostering a more inclusive scientific environment.](#)

MOTIVATE XR players are essential innovation stakeholders within the European Union ecosystems, collaborating to facilitate the open exchange of crucial information in the advanced XR technology sector. Please note that the above identified target audiences might evolve throughout the project.

4 MONITORING AND EVALUATION

Monitoring and evaluation of MOTIVATE XR partners' activities is essential to achieve the project's Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) see Table 4. It ensures alignment with project objectives, promotes accountability by holding partners responsible for their contributions, and provides data for informed decision making. It also helps identify issues early, enhances collaboration among partners, and offers a comprehensive view of progress toward KPIs. By fostering transparency and communication, effective monitoring and evaluation strengthens partnerships and ultimately supports the success of the MOTIVATE XR project.

4.1 KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATORS (KPIs)

The monitoring of communication activities will be executed based on the KPIs, as defined in the Grant Agreement (GA). The following table presents the high-level MOTIVATE XR communication plan. The aim is to accelerate the update of MOTIVATE XR concept, edge topologies and key results for maximising the project's awareness.

Measure	Target Groups	Means	Target KPIs
Project Website	All stakeholders	Online project website designed and developed and constantly updated throughout the project	10k visitors
Social Media Channels	All stakeholders	Online presence in social media channels - LinkedIn and X	5k stakeholders reached 200 monthly impressions
Newsletters	Industry, Academics, EU XR initiatives & Networks, EU-Funded XR projects	Newsletters will be circulated (every 6 months) via email list providing an overview of the main project activities and outcomes	6 newsletters 800 contacts reached

Videos	All stakeholders	Multimedia video podcasts presenting project, its innovation and its key outcomes	3 videos produced 700 views on YouTube
Printed Material, Flyers	All stakeholders	Brochures, leaflet flyers, posters - available online (website) for printing	2k printed copies distributed 4 roll-up banners/posters
Public Events	Citizens, researchers, EU XR initiatives & Networks	Public events with citizens and education/research institutions to inform them about the project and its impact in the everyday life of citizens	4 public events 2 open days at institutions 60 participants per event
Newspapers, Magazines	All stakeholders	Non-technical articles and press releases in local newspaper/magazines to reach the broader audience providing visibility of the project and its achievements	5 press releases in newspaper and magazines
Digital Innovation Hubs (DIH)	Industry specialists, researchers, EU XR initiatives & networks	Promotion of project results in various DIH to amplify the project's outreach for early adoption	20 DIHs contacted
Fora & Blogs	Industry, Academics, EU XR initiatives & Networks, EU-Funded XR projects	Promotion of periodic non-technical reports (publications) to fora and blogs to create awareness on MOTIVATE XR potential and features	5 publications to blogs 3 blogs/for a to post

Other Projects and Activities	Industry, Academics, EU XR initiatives & Networks, EU-Funded XR projects	Liaison with other projects to coordinate the activities in other projects. For these reasons, liaison delegates will be identified for the projects and organisations	5 relevant projects to liaise

TABLE 4: COMMUNICATION PLANS AS PER GA

4.1.1 PROJECT SHAREPOINT

Having all project documents stored in one place is crucial for effective communication and collaboration among the partners. MOTIVATE XR project will be using SharePoint as its repository for all project-related documents and information, where all partners can easily access and share relevant information (Fig.35). [MOTIVATE XR SharePoint](#)

With SharePoint the project coordinator (MAG) will be able to track changes, revisions and versions of documents if required, and ensure that all project partners are working with the same up-to-date information. By having all project documents in one place, the MOTIVATE XR team can streamline their workflow, reduce errors and increase productivity, ultimately leading to better project outcomes and improved collaboration.

FIGURE 35: MOTIVATE XR PROJECT SHAREPOINT

4.1.2 PROJECT KPI SHEET

Maintaining an accessible KPI sheet for all partners to access is vital to ensure transparency, accountability, and collaborative success. This sheet allows partners to track progress and make data-driven decisions. This shared resource not only facilitates informed decision-making but also drives performance improvement and strategic alignment across the entire project team (Fig. 36).

WP2 Communication Plan KPIs (D2.1, D.2.2, D2.3)			
Activity	Target Audience	Means	Target KPIs
Project website	All stakeholders	Online project website designed and developed by F6S, constantly updated throughout the project	Website available by M02 >10.000 visitors by M36
Social media channels	All stakeholders	Online presence in social media channels such as LinkedIn, Twitter, spreading news about the project	>5.000 stakeholders reached >200 monthly impressions
Newsletters	Industry, academics EU XR initiatives & networks, EUfunded XR projects	Newsletters will be circulated via email lists providing an overview of the main project activities and outcomes	>6 newsletters >800 contacts reached
Videos	All stakeholders	Multimedia video podcasts presenting the project, its innovation and its key outcomes	>3 videos produced >700 views in YouTube
Printed material, flyers	All stakeholders	Brochures, leaflets, flyers in events, roll-up banners, posters, also available online for printing through the project's website.	>2.000 printed copies distributed >4 roll-up banners/posters
	Citizens, researchers, EU XR initiatives	Public events with citizens and education/ research institutions to inform them about the project and its impact to the society.	>4 public events >2 open days at institutions >60 participants per

FIGURE 36: MOTIVATE XR KPIs SHEET

4.1.3 SOCIAL MEDIA TRACK

A social media calendar was also created to accurately follow the allocated date for posting (Fig.37). Social media KPIs are monitored accurately every 3 months (Fig.38)

FIGURE 37: SOCIAL MEDIA CALENDAR

FIGURE 38: SOCIAL MEDIA KPIs MONITORING SHEET

4.1.4 MONTHLY RECURRING MEETINGS

Holding a monthly WP2 – Impact, Maximisation and Outreach meeting is essential to discuss the various activities, achievements and concerns of this work package. Regular meetings (scheduled at the end of every month) help identify potential issues early, promote transparency, and allow for collective problem-solving. By prioritising these meetings, we ensure that partners remain engaged

and informed about the progress and future plans of this work package, ultimately aligning our actions and expectations.

4.2 FOSTERING PARTNERS' ENGAGEMENT ON COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

Engaging partners in communication activities and ensuring accurate communication reporting is always a complex task to achieve within a project. Consequently, various guidelines were created with the aim to facilitate exchange and ensure that all partners respect and follow the same process.

To ensure that partners follow the guidelines, a monthly reminder is scheduled at the end of every month (section 4.2.3).

4.2.1 Process Reporting Guidelines

To streamline our communication efforts within the MOTIVATE XR project a Process Reporting Guidelines document (Fig.39) was designed. This document highlights the process of reporting the various communication and dissemination efforts of MOTIVATE XR within the created Partners' Communication and Dissemination respective excel sheet (Fig.40). It emphasises on the importance of each partner's collaboration to achieve the project defined communication and dissemination Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). These guidelines will constantly be updated throughout the project to maximise effectiveness.

FIGURE 39: PARTNERS – PROCESS REPORTING GUIDELINES

Along with the Process Reporting Guidelines, a Partners Input Activities & Monitoring excel sheets were created. These sheets will ensure that every MOTIVATE XR communication and dissemination activities are accurately recorded.

Partner	Description	When? Date	Who? Target Audience Reached	How? Communication Channel	Outcome	Status of Communication	Any promotional material	Links
CETMA	Luca Rizzi New Product Development Area Manager of CETMA presented MotivaxXR project at XR Salento - focusing on user-centric approach	6-Sep-2024	XR Research Comm. Event			Participated		https://www.linkedin.com/posts/cetma_luca-rizzi-new-product-development-area-manager-72385502504591872-kz_77utm_source=organic

FIGURE 40: PARTNERS - COMMUNICATION REPORTING EXCEL SHEET

4.2.2 Collaborative Content Creation Guidelines

As we continue to strengthen our collaboration, it is essential to establish a shared understanding of our content creation process. The Collaborative Content Creation Guidelines document (Fig.41) created is designed to ensure that all partners produce high-quality, cohesive content that resonates with our audience and aligns with our brand values. Key highlights include specifications around formatting standards and style for the project website contents (deliverables, executive summaries, blog articles) and social media posting and resharing.

Moreover, clear expectations around collaboration and review processes are integral to our approach. These guidelines will help streamline communication and ensure timely feedback, allowing for smoother content creation and quicker turnaround times. By working together under these established frameworks, we can maximise our impact and reach within our target audiences. Partners' comprehension and collaboration with these guidelines will not only strengthen our partnership but also help us collectively achieve our goals in delivering meaningful and valuable content.

FIGURE 41: PARTNERS – COLLABORATIVE CONTENT CREATION

Along with the Collaborative Content Creation Guidelines, an excel document (Fig.42) was created to record all website activities and oversee partners’ tasks and contribution in maintaining the website continuously and accurately updated. This document not only assists the communication team (F6S), but also enhances transparency by providing partners with insights into where their input is needed and offers an overview of upcoming plans.

1	Website Blog - Full Editorial Overview								
2	Publish Date (provisional)	Final Author Version Due	Author (Name, Org)	Type of Article	No	Related to any Deliverable or Milestones	Title of Article	Topic/Content/Details	Content Format
3	Blog planning (2024)								
4	18-Sep-24	13-Sep-24	F6S	News	NA	NA	MOTIVATE XR - Website Launch	Showcase project objectives and	Blog post + sneak peal
5	20-Sep-24	31-Aug-24	MAG	Results	D1.1	Project and S&T Management Plan	Diving in MOTIVATE XR management p	define the management structure and	Executive summary + i
6	7-Oct-24	30-Sep-24	F6S	Results	D2.1	Communication Kit V1	Find out more on MOTIVATE XR first cc	Elaborate on Comm Kit developed	Executive summary + i
7	18-Oct-24	30-Sep-24	TUD	Results	D3.1	SSH Framework	Societal, legal and ethical issues that M	elaborate on first analysis of societal, e	Executive summary + i
8	30-Oct-24	30-Sep-24	TUD	Results	D3.3	Industrial User Requirement and Use-Case Scenari	MOTIVATE XR findings to effectively co	Present acquired requirements for tech	Executive summary + i
9	18-Nov-24	1-Nov-24	F6S	Events	NA	NA	SESAR Innovation Days 2024	Sopra Steria to communicate about the Blog post +	Images
10	25-Nov-24	11-Nov-24	F6S	Events	NA	NA	Consortium Meeting Thessaloniki, Greece (Date: 20-22)	- elaborate on how meeti	Blog post + Images
11	6-Dec-24	30-Nov-24	MAG	Results	D2.4	Business Model	Sneak peak of MOTIVATE XR planning	present business modal and strategy	Executive summary + i
12	13-Dec-24	30-Nov-24	F6S	Results	D2.9	Dissemination and Exploitation Plan	Discovering MOTIVATE XR plans to act	presents the project's strategies for aw	Executive summary + i
13	20-Dec-24	30-Nov-24	MAG	Results	D1.2	IPR and Data Management Plan	MOTIVATE XR data management life cycl	describe the data management life cycl	Executive summary + i
14	Blog planning (2025)								
15	9-Jan-25	30-Nov-24	TEC	Results	D3.5	Functional Specifications & Cybersecure Architecture			Executive summary + i
16	23-Jan-25	30-Nov-24	CETMA	Results	D3.7	UX Co-Design Report			Executive summary + i
17	7-Feb-25	30-Nov-24	UPM	Results	D6.1	Continuous Integration Plan and Platform			Executive summary + i
18	24-Feb-25	30-Nov-24	MAG	Results	MS1	Initial Frameworks and Design			Executive summary + i
19	7-Mar-25	28-Feb-25							
20	27-Mar-25	20-Mar-25							
21	10-Apr-25	3-Apr-25							
22	30-Apr-25	23-Apr-25							

FIGURE 42: OVERVIEW OF WEBSITE BLOG POST SCHEDULING

4.2.3 Recurring Email Prepared

To ensure that partners adhere to important communication rules and remain informed with communication activities, a recurring email is scheduled after every WP2 Monthly meeting (Fig.43). These emails are crucial to foster a collaborative approach among the partners – reminding them of

important activities coming up, to accurately and continuously update the communication activities sheet, and refer to the process reporting guidelines and other important documents. This email gathers various important links (Communication Kit, Process Reporting, and Collaborative Content Creation Guidelines) partners might need to accurately communicate about the project and report any activities. It will also provide a few important social media links that partners could like and reshare to maximise reach.

FIGURE 43: MONTHLY COMMUNICATION RECURRING EMAIL

4.3 PERFORMANCE MEASUREMENT

Performance measurement is a vital component of a communication plan as it ensures alignment with strategic goals, holds team members accountable, and identifies areas for improvement. By quantifying the impact of communication efforts, MOTIVATE XR ensures that informed decisions are taken and that strategies are accurately adjusted to maximise effectiveness. MOTIVATE XR will be using two performance measuring tools:

MATOMO: is an open-source web analytics platform that allows users to track and analyse website traffic while ensuring data ownership and privacy. It will be used to measure real-time MOTIVATE XR website traffic and user interactions, and for reporting to enhance insights into user behaviour (Fig.44).

Social Media Metrics: are quantifiable data points that measure the performance and engagement of content across social platforms. Key metrics include likes, shares, comments, reach,

impressions and follower growth, which will be essential data when assessing the campaign effectiveness and audience interaction (Fig.45).

FIGURE 44: MATOMO PLATFORM ANALYTICS

FIGURE 45: SOCIAL MEDIA PLATFORM METRICS

5 CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable (D2.1) outlines the first release plan for the MOTIVATE XR communication activities, strategic approach, as well as highlighting the various communication materials available in the Communication Kit V1, that will be used to engage with a diverse range of stakeholders throughout the project lifetime. This document aims to structure and coordinate communication activities and efforts to ensure that the defined objectives of the project are met.

This document should be used as a strategic plan for all MOTIVATE XR communication activities, and guidelines for reporting should be followed by all partners to ensure effective results. The communication strategy will be updated accordingly with the new project's development and opportunities in the next iteration D2.2 Communication Kit V2 due for M18.

APPENDIX A

Communication and dissemination Guidelines for MOTIVATE XR project partners

Process Reporting Guidelines:

IMPORTANCE OF THIS DOCUMENT

These comprehensive guidelines are designed to streamline our communication and dissemination efforts within the MOTIVATE XR project. This document highlights the process of filling in the **WP2-Impact Maximisation and Outreach** [Partners Input_WP2_Activities & Monitoring Mastersheet](#).

The data collected will be essential for the WP2 reporting activities and [KPIs](#) monitoring throughout the duration of the project. Hence, we kindly ask for each partner's consideration and input to successfully achieve the project targets.

Note: A monthly reminder “to fill in the sheets” will be sent to all partners

1. DIFFERENCE BETWEEN COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

Communication is about talking with people; promoting MOTIVATE XR and its results beyond the project's own community; and communicating our work in ways that non-specialists can easily understand. Inform, promote and communicate your activities and results.

Example: you can include any kind of online communication/promotion of the project or participation in events for the general public or campaign etc. It's simply any activity where MOTIVATE XR is promoted e.g. raising awareness and visibility about the project's mission and goals.

Dissemination is about sharing results with people. It's about transferring MOTIVATE XR's knowledge and outputs/results/progress to those who can best make use of them; and maximising the impact of our work. Raise awareness, let others know what and how the project is going, inform, educate the community, engage, get input/feedback from the community, promote, “sell” the project outputs/results. Therefore, the target audience of dissemination activities is any potential user of the project results: the scientific community, stakeholders, industry, policy makers, investors, civil society, etc.

Example: Participating in an event/conference and presenting the project results to local community groups and other valuable stakeholders.

For your referral:

[Read More 1](#) , [Read More 2](#)

2. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

These 2 sheets (see section 1.1 and 1.2) should **be updated monthly** with every communication and dissemination activity carried out by each partner throughout the project. Please add your activities if not directly after the activity at least **within the month**.

Every communication and dissemination activity where MOTIVATE XR is promoted somehow **must be recorded** in their respective sheets. (e.g. any website articles or events / workshop you participated in...).

○ **Communication Activities**

Comms Activities: select this table for any general activities to communicate the project, usually for a wider audience, and using existing communication channels (Website, Print materials, Press release, Media article, Newsletter, Interview, Video, TV/Radio campaign, Event, Exhibition, Other).

Please make sure to:

- Fill in the columns with as much detail as possible. Be concise and **add any useful links** to the communication activities as required.
- In the sheet, column “Outcome” please add numbers or specific results of your activity e.g. estimated views on the website, number of attendees etc.
- If the communication activity has any relevant pictures or other important material, create a respective folder within the “**MTXR_Comm.Activities**” folder with format: **Date_Partner_CommActivityName**. Please don’t forget to add the link of the above folder in the Comm Activities Sheet.

○ **Dissemination Activities**

Diss Activities: select this table for activities presenting any results of the project, usually to audiences who are potential users and adopters of these results. These activities include Conferences, Education and training events, Meetings, Clustering activities, Collaboration with EU-funded projects, Other scientific collaboration, Other.

If you are not sure what kind of dissemination activities you should report, please do refer to the [project dissemination KPI’s](#) coming from GA under tab 2 (Task 2.1 KPI’s). Still, if you conducted other, not listed dissemination activities, please update the table as well.

Please make sure to:

- Create a respective folder within the “**MTXR_Diss.Activities**” folder with format: **Date_Partner_DissActivityName**. Please include any relevant images of activities, information, invitation, agenda, written content etc.
- Please don’t forget to add the link of the above folder in the Diss Activities Sheet.

3. POTENTIAL EVENTS LIST

All partners are requested to actively communicate and disseminate the MOTIVATE XR project. Events can include conferences, courses, training, and opportunities either promoted by the project or attended by project partners.

The [Potential Events List](#) sheet was created to gather all the **potential or confirmed events** you might be participating in/co-exhibiting/presenting/organising. This sheet will provide an overview of interesting and relevant events happening within the project's duration, to facilitate communication and be aware if any support from F6S is required.

Note: This sheet should **continuously be updated** throughout the whole project duration.

2.1 Event Activities

This section highlights and defines the activities that should and will be carried out for both the partners and the F6S Team, so the events are properly spotlighted on the project website and social media.

After confirmation, partners are encouraged to disseminate events related to the MOTIVATE XR project in three steps:

1. **Before the Event:** Once attendance/participation to an event is confirmed, partners should add the relevant event information in the Potential Event List sheet. If any material (e.g., a roll-up, flyer, or other visual) is required for dissemination activities, partners should mention it in the respective column and notify F6S by leaving a comment tagging melissa@f6s.com.

If there is any new/specific material request, partner should mention it during the WP2 Monthly Meeting. If you cannot attend the meeting, please send an email to melissa@f6s.com at **least 3 weeks (appx. 15 working days) prior to the event** (adaptations to existing materials may be handled within 2 weeks) to ensure successful promotion and engagement of a wider audience.

Once F6S has the information:

- 1 week before event: If appropriate, F6S will post an announcement of the project/partner's participation on LinkedIn and X.
 - 3-4 working days before event: If requested, F6S will produce the material, iterating it with the partner.
2. **During the Event:** Partner should create a respective folder within the "[MTXR_Diss.Activities](#)" folder with format: **Date_Partner_DissActivityName**. Please include any relevant images of activities and written content.

Partners should add information (short description of how event is going etc. including photos) in the event folder created and notify the F6S team to highlight their participation in the event.

F6S will then prepare a Social Media post to update the audience on the evolution of the event along with the pictures received

3. **After the Event:** Partners who attended the event should fill in relevant information in the [Diss Activities](#) sheet along with the link to the folder created within the "[MTXR_Diss.Activities](#)" folder.

Partners especially those exhibiting, presenting, and organising events, are encouraged to write a blog post to promote the results and outcomes of the event on the website.

- **Within 3 working days after the event:** The partner who attended the event is encouraged to draft an article (1 400 – 2 100 words in length) to promote the event (add prepared article within the folder created for the event). Once ready please send an email to melissa@f6s.com.
- If the partner does not want to draft the article, F6S will prepare one LinkedIn post and share it with the photos.

Collaborative Content Creation Guidelines

IMPORTANCE OF THIS DOCUMENT

As we continue to strengthen our collaboration, it's essential to establish a shared understanding of our content creation process. These guidelines are designed to ensure that all partners produce high-quality, cohesive content that resonates with our audience and aligns with our brand values. Key highlights include specifications around formatting standards and style.

Moreover, clear expectations around collaboration and review processes are integral to our approach. These guidelines will help streamline communication and ensure timely feedback, allowing for smoother content creation and quicker turnaround times. By working together under these established frameworks, we can maximise our impact and reach within our target audiences. Your comprehension and collaboration with these guidelines will not only strengthen our partnership but also help us collectively achieve our goals in delivering meaningful and valuable content.

Please note that these guidelines will be adapted throughout the project as needed to further enhance our collaboration.

1. WEBSITE FEEDBACK REPORTING

Partners are welcome to provide feedback or ask for modifications, at any time throughout the project duration. Please fill in the [Website Feedback](#) sheet and notify F6S by leaving a comment - tagging melissa@f6s.com.

The file should be filled as per the following or refer to Figure 1

- **Name and Organisation:** identify yourself and your organisation.
- **Website Page:** identify the specific page you are referring to (e.g. "About Us") and add the link to the page on the website.
- **Comment/Feedback:** describe clearly what and how the page should be modified.
- **Screenshot/Image:** add a screenshot or an image of the issue or desired outcome (add notes or circle on image - be precise on where you want changes made).
- **Date:** the current date when you are reporting the comment.
- **Status:** F6S will follow up and update the status in addressing the comment.

Website Feedback Sheet - Partners Input
 To facilitate networking and collaboration, this sheet will allow partners to provide feedback on MOTIVATE XR Website pages and content
 If any doubt please refer to Collaborative Content Creation Reporting Guidelines or reach out to F6S
 Please leave a comment by tagging melissa@f6s.com in your respective feedback row, so we are aware of the new addition

Partner (Name, Org)	Website Page / Section <i>Add link to page</i>	Comment / Feedback	Insert a screenshot or image (optional) <i>(Person, Person Title, Partner Org.)</i>	Date <i>DD-MM-YYYY</i>	Status <i>F6S will fill this part</i>
Melissa, F6S	About - Partners	Please amend short paragraph from "MOTIVATE XR brings... operations." to short example of what to amend on the website.		6/9/2024	

Fig 1: Partner Website Feedback Sheet

2. WEBSITE CONTENT CREATION - INTERNAL PROCESS

F6S is the main partner responsible for maintaining the website but will count on each partner's collaboration to produce relevant and meaningful content. Throughout the project, partners will contribute to the website content in several ways, as described in this section.

There are two main types of content that will be added to the website:

1. **New Pages and Deliverables:** will elaborate on the project's approach and results, as per the Website Timeline.
2. **Blog Articles:** will describe results, events, and insights.

F6S plans to add content to the website periodically, following the project's timeline and results. Please refer to the **[Blog – Full Editorial Calendar](#)** for more details.

(please note that this Editorial Calendar will be updated to align with the project progress)

2.1 NEW PAGES

For each new website pages iteration, the following activities will take place.

- 8 working days before the following WP4 regular meeting: F6S prepares a first version of the content, i.e. page with all the elements (text, visuals, videos etc.), and sends it to all partners.
- 3 working days before WP4 regular meeting: Partners fill in the website feedback form with any comments about the new content.
- During the WP4 regular meeting: we all perform a walkthrough on the second iteration of the content and discuss any open feedback provided.
- 5 working days after the WP4 regular meeting: the new content becomes available online.

2.2 DELIVERABLES

All deliverables produced and submitted will be mentioned on the project's website and social media as per the Blog - Full Editorial Calendar.

The leading partner of the deliverable is responsible for providing a **Public Executive Summary** and should be available to iterate the content and visuals with the F6S team.

The Executive Summary will be used in two ways:

- **The initial or full version:** will be published as an article on the website. For public deliverables, the article will allow the downloading option of the entire deliverable, and
- **A shorter version or an excerpt:** will be created for social media purposes (LinkedIn).

The executive summary of the deliverable should comply to the following criteria:

- 1 400 – 2 100 words in length
- Include a title under 60 characters
- Provide a meaningful overview of the deliverable, including the topic, approach, and main conclusions
- Text should be appropriate for the public, avoid technical jargon
- Include a high-resolution figure representative of the work.

2.3 BLOG ARTICLES

Partners are invited to write blog posts related to their activities within the project, e.g. any work realised, or events attended, or topics aligned with the project's focus areas. F6S has prepared a **[Blog – Full Editorial Calendar](#)** that demonstrate the plan of the various blog posts scheduled for the website.

As seen in the editorial calendar, apart from blog posts about deliverables or events, several gaps in the schedule were identified (in orange). F6S believes that potential blog posts on relevant topics should be published during these gaps to maintain website traffic and engagement. Partners are encouraged to contribute to the successful planning of these topics and are welcome to suggest any ideas or topics they might have.

Note: when choosing a topic please align topic with any kind of deliverable or milestones published or that will soon be publish

For these blog posts, the process activities will be as follow:

- Partner selects a topic, defines a title for the post, fill in the sheet [Website Blog Post](#) and tag melissa@f6s.com
- Create a respective folder in the "[MTXR_Website_Blog_Post](#)" folder with format: **Date_Partner_BlogTitle**. Please include any relevant images/diagrams (if any required for

post) and written content. Please don't forget to add the link to the folder in the [Website Blog Post Sheet](#).

- F6S discusses schedule with the proposing partner and introduces the blog post on the editorial calendar.
- Partner prepares the complete blog post and sends to F6S on "final version due date" as indicated in the Invited Blog Posts. Please respect the **Final Author Due Date** to deliver content, so we can publish as planned (bear in mind that we need time for final revision before publishing if needed).
- The proposing partner should be available for any iteration needed in the week before posting.
- F6S publishes the blog post on the website and social media channels

Any blog post should comply with the following structure:

- **Title:** Create a catchy and descriptive title that reflects the essence of the post. Incorporate keywords related to the project and keep it under 60 characters.
- **Introduction:** Start with an engaging introduction that sets the stage for the post's content and draws readers in.
- **Content Development:** Choose a specific theme or topic related to the project to focus the post. Include, if appropriate, references and links to relevant material (e.g. reports, websites, technical reports, SDOs, other projects). Include a high-resolution figure representative of the work.
- **Visual representations:** Please include in high-resolution any relevant diagram, images, videos etc. Associated with the post.
- **Conclusion:** Summarise the key points discussed in the post.

In addition, the blog post must:

- be 1 400 – 2 100 words in length;
- include a meta description under 155 characters; and
- Ensure the article is concise, clear, and well-organised, avoid jargon or overly technical language.
- Use subheadings, bullet points, or numbered lists to improve readability and structure.

3. SOCIAL MEDIA POSTING AND RESHARING

Understanding how to post and reshare MOTIVATE XR post on your organisation or personal channel is crucial for expanding reach, boosting engagement, and maintaining visibility. By posting and resharing, partners can distribute content to a broader audience, encourage interactions, and reinforce key messages. This practice also fosters collaboration opportunities with partners and promotes brand consistency, which is vital for establishing credibility and trust.

Please note that whenever posting or resharing MOTIVATE XR posts, links to MOTIVATE XR website (www.motivatexr.eu) and/or channels must be included: [LinkedIn](#), [X](#), and [YouTube](#).

For those of you that aren't sure what I'm talking about when I say resharing, please find below a few steps to help:

- Underneath the post, select button Repost and select "Repost with your thoughts" (Fig.2)
- Add your own text, for example
- Follow MOTIVATE XR and visit the website www.motivatexr.eu to stay up-to-date as we embark on our journey to redefine the XR ecosystem
- Happy to collaborate on the MOTIVATE XR project! For the next years, we will be working on (share something about your role in the project or the project achievement your organisation contributed to)
- Add a few (4-5) relevant hashtags from the list below and feel free to add any hashtags that resonate with your post that aren't mentioned below.

#XR #XRauthoring #XRtraining #AI #VR #training #assistance #smartheadset #virtualreality #experience #HorizonEurope #technology #researchandinnovation #integrated #aerospace #manufacturing #collaboration #technology #research #HorizonEurope #usercentric

- Tag other people (team members) and organisations to maximise reach and engagement.
- Feel free to comment on the Original MOTIVATE XR post, mentioning your participation, or thoughts about the announcement made etc.

Fig 2: Repost with your thoughts on LinkedIn

4. CONTACT DETAILS

WP2 - Impact Maximisation and Outreach

F6S Innovation

- [Mateusz Kowacki](#)
- [Melissa Tang](#)

Please include both contacts when reaching out.